

plex formed through hydrogen bonding, the complex being more stable in catechol than in resorcinol. This is in agreement with the previous work.

The thermodynamic parameters were calculated using Eyring equation from the data of Table 1, and are shown in Table 2. The energy of activation for the decarboxylation of oxalic acid in resorcinol is higher than in catechol, and it appears that the reaction mechanism in these solvents is identical. The entropy of activation is much more positive in resorcinol than in catechol, which indicates that the complex is more stable in catechol and the association is weaker in resorcinol. The thermodynamic parameters for the decarboxylation of oxalic acid falls in the same line (Table 2, columns 2 and 4). The high values of enthalpy of activation also indicate that a weaker attraction exists between the solute and solvent for the decarboxylation of oxalic acid in resorcinol. The structures of the complexes can be written as

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Electronic Property of Photosensitive Film Formation on Silver in Aqueous Solution of Hydrogen Sulphide

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SILVER reacts extremely slowly with aqueous hydrogen sulphide solution in free access to oxygen giving a greyish black film of Ag_2S . The film exhibits all the chemical properties of Ag_2S . In the present work the electronic property of the film has been studied.

Experimental :

Silver specimen of composition 99.8% Ag was used. It was cleaned and polished according to the method suggested by Champion². The cleaned silver coupon was immersed in saturated aqueous solution of hydrogen sulphide. The two surfaces of the treated silver plate were connected to a ballistic galvanometer, one surface was exposed to sunlight and the other was kept in the dark. The photocurrent produced was noted with time interval of exposure in seconds. The intensity of light at the exposed surface was 22500 lumens. The size of the silver specimen was 3×3 cms (22 S.W.G.).

Fig. 1.

Discussion :

Rohde and Hermann³ have studied the photoelectric effects of silver sulphide single crystals. Silver sulphide is sensitive to luminous or U.V. radiations. K. Friedrich and A. Leroux⁴ have found that argentite is decomposed by exposure to sunlight. The surface becomes covered with a fine dust when exposed to intense solar light.

In the present work a film of Ag_2S was formed by long exposure of silver specimen in aqueous hydrogen sulphide solution in access to oxygen and light according to the following reaction

According to Barschevskii⁵ the photocurrent and the spectral characteristics ($i = f\lambda$) for AgBr and other silver halide varies with layer thickness. The cause of such variation is the changes in the relative number of surface light absorption centres at the surface and internal photoelectric effects such as acid volume centres (dissociating excitons).

Fig. 2.

According to the literature no visible image formation takes place in an Ag_2S film by the action of sunlight. Contrary to this it has been found in the present study that Ag_2S films formed by the action of H_2S water on silver are photosensitive and produce visible images without the application of a developer. Thus, upon exposure to sunlight an image was formed of the marking on the glass container through which the radiation was passed (Fig. 1). In another experiment the two surfaces of the treated plates were connected to a sensitive ballistic galvanometer and the current produced when one surface of the treated plate was exposed to sunlight was measured as a function of time. A typical graph obtained is displayed in Fig. 2. The most interesting feature of the curve is the reversal of polarity. Similar reversals of polarity have also been reported by Tamura et al⁶ who measured the photocurrent in compacted and sintered AgBr powder and found the forward currents to increase to a maximum and then to decrease to an equilibrium value.

The probable explanation is that Ag_2S which is formed in excess of photo-adsorbed oxygen is converted to Ag_2O and SO_2 according to the reaction

During this conversion the photocurrent increases and after a layer of Ag_2O film is formed on top of Ag_2S , the current levels off. The levelling of current may be due to the semiconducting layer of Ag_2S and Ag_2O . Ag_2S being an 'n' type semiconductor and Ag_2O 'p' type semiconductor; form a *pn* junction.

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Abnormal Products in a Condensation Reaction

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N-Hydroxymethylphthalimide has been reported to condense with primary aromatic amines yielding N-arylamino-methyl-phthalimides in good yields¹. This reaction was employed to prepare N-(2-chloro-4-nitroaniline) methylphthalimide (I) by treating 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline with N-hydroxymethylphthalimide. However this condensation reaction did not furnish the expected product (I). From the reaction mixture two substances were isolated: a white crystalline solid (A), soluble in ethanol, m.p. 229° and a yellow crystalline solid (B), insoluble in ethanol and sparingly soluble in glacial acetic acid, decomposing above 260°.

The infrared spectrum of A indicated presence of NH (3175 cm^{-1}) and C=O groups (1770 cm^{-1}) and absence of nitro group and was identical with the infrared of phthalimide. Its mixed m.p. with phthalimide did not show any depression. The elemental analysis was in accordance with phthalimide. Therefore substance A appears to be phthalimide.

The infrared spectrum of B showed absorptions due to NH (3378 cm^{-1}) and nitro groups (1344 , 1500 cm^{-1}) and was devoid of C=O absorption. The elemental data was in agreement with the proposed structure (II). Its extreme insolubility in